

УДК 335.722.24

Sven-Olof Yrjö Collin, Jenny Ahlberg
**NEPOTISM – ITS PROS AND CONS
IN FAMILY BUSINESS**

Nepotism constitutes the essence of a family business, where it creates both positive and negative effects on the family and the firm. In this second paper, in a series of two, we present a matrix of family business nepotism, where we derive positive and negative implications of nepotism for the family and for the firm. The matrix is applied on three case studies, using the terminology of the first paper (Collin & Ahlberg, 2022). We present propositions induced from the analysis and suggest that nepotism can be managed, for the benefit of the family and the firm.

Key words: family business, nepotism, governance

Свен-Олоф Коллін, Дженні Ахлбер. Непотизм: переваги та недоліки для сімейного бізнесу.

Непотизм розглянуто як сутність сімейного бізнесу, як те, що може мати або позитивний, або негативний вплив на родинні відносини та на партнерські взаємини. Це друга стаття із серії статей на цю тематику, в ній представлена матриця непотизму в сімейному бізнесі, яка показує його переваги та недоліки. Матриця розроблена на основі висвітлення трьох компонентів з використанням термінології непотизму, що було предметом дослідження першої статті. На основі аналізу зроблено припущення про те, що непотизм покращує відносини в родині та сприяє розвитку бізнесу.

Ключові слова: сімейний бізнес, непотизм, управління.

Introduction

Nepotism, i.e., a tendency to treat individuals preferably due to family relationships, independently of contribution (Webb, Ketchen, & Ireland, 2010; Collin & Ahlberg, 2012), competence, productivity or performance is the constitutive element of family business. It is what defines a family business: “The family business is a business governed and/or managed with the intention to shape and pursue the vision of the business held by a dominant coalition controlled by members of the same family or a small number of families in a manner that is potentially sustainable across generations of the family or families” (Chua, Chrisman, and Sharma,

1999:25). The sustainability that Chua and colleagues refer to is nepotism, i.e., the transfer of ownership and very often the management of the firm to the coming generation.

Nepotism is, however, rather differently treated by the public opinion, where nepotism on the ownership side, i.e., heritage of the corporation's shares, and therefore the governance of the corporation, is considered to be a good thing, while to inherit positions within the firm, typically management positions, is less accepted, even stigmatized. Indeed, sometimes the word nepotism is reserved only for the allocation of family members in the organisational structure of the family firm, where this action has negative connotations (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012). Indeed, Mhatre, Riggio & Riggio (2012, p.175) state: "...there is no such thing as 'good nepotism'".

In the present paper, number 2 in a series of 2, we will argue that nepotism has good and bad sides, and that nepotism can be, should be, or even is, managed. In our first paper (Collin & Ahlberg, 2022) we contributed to the study of family business and nepotism by offering a typology of nepotism that described nepotism on the family side and on the firm side. One advantage of such a terminology is not only that the phenomenon of nepotism receives an opportunity to be treated in a systematic way, but also that the treatment will be without values in disguise, for example, those just mentioned.

In the present paper we continue our effort to analyse nepotism. This time, however, we put attention on values. We analyse nepotism from the point of view if it has positive or negative effects for the family and for the firm. We include both the firm and the family since a family business implies a necessary link between family and firm, where excluding one of them would make it impossible to understand the family business. Our contribution here is a list of positive and negative effects of nepotism. Additionally, we analyse three case studies, using the terminology of the first paper (Collin & Ahlberg, 2022) and the list of effects in this paper, reaching some empirically induced propositions about nepotism and family business. Finally, we indicate that nepotism is not a given in family business, but that it can be managed.

Our main contribution with the two papers is that there is no reason to put a stigma on nepotism, but to highlight that it can be used as a concept that can reveal the nature of the family firm.

The paper starts with a list of factors that are created by nepotism and that have negative or positive implications for the family and the firm. Then we present the three cases and analyse them, using the terminology and the list of effects. In conclusion we propose four strategies to manage nepotism.

Derivation of the Matrix of Family Business Nepotism

We introduced the paper by showing that nepotism can be regarded as both a positive factor and a negative factor. Our aim is not to stigmatize nepotism or to hail it, but instead try to treat it with a non-interest towards its positive and negative effects, and independently of any value connected to it. Our aim is to find consequences of nepotism that it can produce in a family business.

It could be claimed that nepotism is a constitutive trait of the family firm organizational form if defining it as a firm that is governed by a family and for a family with the goal of supporting present and future members of the family (cf. Le Breton-Miller & Miller, 2008), i.e. if there is the purpose of considering the family and the firm in a reciprocal relationship. In that definition nepotism lies at the heart of the family business since simultaneous care for the family and the firm is one of the constituents. In that sense, nepotism influences both the family and the firm. We will therefore structure our exploration of the effects of nepotism into family effects and firm effects.

Since nepotism has been doomed as mainly having negative implications, we continue the evaluative tradition by structuring our exploration due to perceived or found negative and positive implications. It is, however, important to understand that all evaluations include acceptance of a specific value, thus, to structure an exploration of nepotism through evaluation is highly controversial. Accepting the goal of the dominant family owner, nepotistic actions could in fact be considered as being efficient given a non-financial goal orientation and inefficient only when they counteract the goal orientation of the family firm owner. One value we assume is the right of the owner to decide on the goal of the corporation. But we also

acknowledge other values, such as meritocracy as a societal value and firm survival as a value of employees. From literature, experience and logical derivation, we have created a matrix of family business nepotism, which will be described below.

In this matrix we assume nepotism to be a tendency to treat individuals preferably due to family relationships, independently of contribution, competence, productivity or performance. Even if the most negative description of family member's behaviour (Schulze et al., 2001) include children with pure exploitative actions, i.e., serial nepotism (Collin & Ahlberg, 2022), we also consider a disposition towards reciprocity (Neyer & Lang, 2003). With these dispositions, we can explore the family as having characteristics resembling to those of a clan with a normative congruence and with an exchange system where the currency is qualitative and not quantitative (i.e., clan nepotism, as described in Collin & Ahlberg, 2022). Even if nepotism implies unequal exchange, we assume some kind of exchange, including solidarity, a lack of utilitarian drives (Kragh, 2012), and obligations to reciprocate (Jaskiewicz et al, 2013). For example, a child given the advantage of being installed as vice CEO without due competence and former performance in the firm will be indebted to the family or has earned the position through performance in the family and not in the firm.

Since family business implies unclear borders between family and firm, we believe that the reciprocity can cross these borders, e.g., a family member can earn benefits in the firm, but has to assume costs in the family, or vice versa. From the point of view of the firm, it creates the impression of being serial nepotism, i.e., given a position without contribution, but from the point of view of the family, it could be a position given due to strong contribution to the family, i.e., clan nepotism.

The family business is characterized by two systems, the firm and the family. Thus, to evaluate consequences of nepotism, we have to consider effects on both the firm and the family. Table 1 shows effects of nepotism that are positive or negative towards the family or towards the family firm.

Positive implications of nepotism for the family

Cohesion: Within the family, nepotism can create cohesion to the extent that individual family members adhere to family values. By adhering to the

Table 1: Matrix of Family Business Nepotism

	The family	The firm
Positive implications	<i>Cohesion Incentives Reproduction of owners</i>	<i>Engaged workers Predictability Familianness production Creation of altruism Long-term investments Recruitment savings Control of employees Clan responsibility Governance certainty Family competence Tacit knowledge management</i>
Negative implications	<i>Demoralizing De-competence Imprisonment</i>	<i>Disincentives Demoralizing Positional unproductivity Clan responsibility</i>

values and by contributing to the family, the individual family member will increase its probability of being included in the firm. This positive reinforcement will promote family values and the family. There exists some selection in the family, i.e., expecting nepotistic selection (Collin & Ahlberg, 2022), implying that not all family members will be given the same advantage. But contribution will be expected and could influence the nepotistic selection.

Incentives: With nepotism, especially with clan nepotism where contributions are expected, family members have incentives to contribute to the family, with norm congruence and other forms of contributions, since it will increase the probability of inclusion in the firm.

Reproduction of owners: An important goal of a family firm is to keep the firm in the family (Lane et al, 2006). With nepotism, individuals become part of the firm, get knowledge about the firm and get attachment to the firm that makes them prepared to assume ownership in the next generation. Thus, nepotism could be an active part of succession planning.

Positive implications of nepotism for the firm

Engaged workers: Family members employed at the firm could be more engaged and involved (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012), being more flexible toward work tasks, working hours, wage level, and having lower probability to leave the firm.

Predictability: Family members will inherit certain positions, and maybe it is even known which family member who will inherit which position. Since family members move faster to executive positions and reach the top management level faster than non-family employees (Salvato, Minichilli & Piccarreta, 2012), a strong signal is given in the organization about management intentions. This creates predictability, thus reducing uncertainty, in the organisation (Dickson, Nieminen & Biermeier-Hanson, 2012).

Familiness production: Nepotism could create the resource of familiness, i.e., strong values held by the family that are disseminated in the organization (Distelberg & Blow, 2011), through nepotistic impregnation. This can in turn create loyalty and trust towards the family and the firm by the employees and other stakeholders.

Creation of altruism: Nepotism in terms of taking care of family members could be expanded to encompass all members of the firm and thus lead to firm altruism, i.e., to support others in the firm depending on their needs, or lead to paternalism, to support others in the firm independently of their needs. Thus, nepotism could lead to a culture of caring not only for family members, but also for other employees (Karra, Tracey, & Phillips, 2006). One outcome of this caring culture could be a culture of trust and solidarity in the organization (Vallejo, 2008), that could produce feelings of justice, even if the firm is based on nepotism (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012). It is conceivable that both familiness production and creation of altruism is supported by the process of employment of non-family members, where attraction, selection and attrition all support inclusion of employees supporting family values and culture (van Hooft & Stout, 2012) and excluding those not attracted to those values (Dickson, Nieminen & Biermeier-Hanson, 2012).

Long-term investments: Since nepotism implies that family members, present and future, will be given advantages, there has to be a firm to

exploit, thus nepotism promotes long-term investments, including a long-term perspective and the aim of transferring the firm to one's children (Lane, et al 2006). Or, with modern jargon, it creates a sustainable business, at least on the economic side.

Recruitment savings: Recruiting family members to positions in the firm reduces costs spent on surveying the market for applicants and on evaluating and selecting them (Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012). In this respect, nepotism has traits of the internal labour market (Doeringer & Piore, 1971).

Control of employees: There is higher probability that the employed family member will be influenced by the family culture compared to other employees. The family member will therefore also participate in the reproduction of this culture (Dickson, Nieminen & Biermeier-Hanson, 2012). Thus, nepotism contributes to reproducing the family business culture.

Clan responsibility: All family members belong to the clan organization of the family, which could imply collective responsibility and solidarity. Consequences of one family member's actions will be assumed by the family. This implies that non-family employees are independent of the actual family member's capacity to compensate for misconduct since the responsibility is on the family as a whole.

Governance certainty: Nepotism creates reproduction of potential family owners, thus securing continued family influence over the firm (Vinton, 1998; Webb et al., 2010) and the continuation of the norms of the family.

Family competence: The employed family member carries a combination of functional and family competence. While nepotism could imply that family members not competent for a position will be put at that position, nepotism implies that this individual can have intimate knowledge of the family, its values, norms and intentions with the firm, and could have access to the networks of the family (Mhatre, Riggio & Riggio, 2012). Thus, at the price of less functional competence, the family member employed could carry significant family competence.

Tacit knowledge management: Tacit knowledge, that can constitute a competitive advantage, will be more easily transferred within the firm, exploited and protected when nepotism characterise the firm (Jaskiewicz

et al 2013). If clan nepotism dominates, there will be a high level of trust and committed interaction characterised by rich communication, which all facilitate usage of tacit knowledge.

Negative implications of nepotism for the family

De-moralizing: If the family is not a clan with an exchange system, where members have to contribute to the family or to the firm, which has been our assumption above, then there is serial nepotism, i.e., all family members are treated the same way independently of contribution (Collin & Ahlberg, 2022). Serial nepotism can become demoralizing for those family individuals that are prepared to perform, i.e., characterised by clan nepotism.

De-competence: Family members that experience a high probability to get employment in the firm will invest less in education because 1. They do not need the human capital investment the education represents, and 2. They do not need the signal of ability that an education creates (Gevrek & Gevrek, 2010). Interestingly enough, in the Gevrek & Gevrek (2010) data they found this factor to be strong in the case of men, and weak or absent in case of women, only related to the female having a non-professional family firm father. One could also add a third factor: 3. Since they know what position they will get in the future, they do not need to diversify their educational investment, which will make them much more focused in their studies, lacking the diversified set of abilities through education that a non-family student have to attain. Additionally, they will have lower level of environment exploration, thus being reduced in diverse views (van Hooft & Stout, 2012). Bloom & van Reenen (2007) found lower financial performance in firms using primogeniture, i.e., preference of managerial positions to the oldest son, which could be due to a lack of interest in competence investments by the oldest sons.

Imprisonment: Individuals of the family could experience that they should enter, or that they are forced to enter the family firm. While they experience the opportunity of the family firm, they also experience a limitation of their life choices (Muchinsky, 2012). As employees they experience higher exposure to control, both from family members and from employees. All in all, a sense of imprisonment can be experienced, that can reduce commitment and engagement.

Negative implications of nepotism for the firm

Disincentives: Non-family members have no incentives for performance directed toward promotion to positions that is clearly signalled as being reserved for family members (Bertrand & Schoar, 2006; Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012; cf. Lubatkin, Schulze, Ling, & Dino, 2005).

Demoralizing: In meritocracy organizations, advantages that are not related to performance could be considered to be unfair and a mark of injustice, which demoralizes the non-family members of the organization (Barnett & Kellermanns, 2006; van Hooft & Stout, 2012; Schulze et al., 2001; Spranger, Colarelli, Dimotakis, Jacob & Arvey, 2012).

Positional unproductivity: Family members recruited due to nepotism do not perform in their position as good as an individual recruited due to former performance. This will lead to lower productivity by them (Lubatkin et al., 2005) and create stress among non-family employees (van Hooft & Stout, 2012).

Clan responsibility: Nepotism implies clan responsibility among the family members. When there could be a conflict between family and firm, a family employee can be expected to first and foremost promote the family interest, which could be at the expense of the needs of the firm.

Strategy limitations: Strategy is assumed to be a function of internal resources, external opportunities and threats, moderated by managerial opportunism directed towards growth. In the case of family firms, the strategy could additionally be a function of the family needs, expressed through nepotistic supply. Growth incentives could be due to a pressure from the nepotistic supply interest and not guided by exploitation of resources of the firm or environment. Additionally, strategic opportunism, i.e., the willingness and the capacity to develop new businesses and to exploit opportunities in the environment and in the organisation (Collin & Smith, 2007) could be limited due to resource limitations that constitute the family, be it cognitive or network limitations. In this way, nepotism have similar effects as have been found through the similar attraction paradigm studies (Dickson, Nieminen & Biermeier-Hanson, 2012).

Summarizing the implications of nepotism, we find an equal number of three items on the family side, but nine items that can be regarded as

positive and four regarded as negative for the firm. While the strength of the implications will deem if they are positive overall for the firm and the family, the pure number as such indicates that nepotism overall has positive contributions. Else, how could family firms exist in a competitive environment?

When inspecting the implications of nepotism, it appears that most positive implications have a character of certainty and care. In the family as well as in the firm and with stakeholders, family impregnation can imply certainty and care taking. At the same time, the negative implications have a character of less demanding work climate and less family member engagement. At first sight this could create an image of a corporation and a family with low level of engagement and intensity. On the other hand, those that could assume the highest risk, those that could be most innovative are both those with high level of risk attitude, which probably are not fostered in a family firm, but also those that felt that their life and their investments are not at stake when producing a risk. Thus, it is not possible to draw any directional hypothesis whether the implications of nepotism will create an innovative or a conservative organisation. By itself it appears not to be possible to draw a conclusion that nepotism creates a competitive advantage or disadvantage for the firm. Jaskiewicz et al (2013) claims that there are different forms of nepotism. We could suggest another direction for finding reasons why family firms exist, and that is that nepotism could differ, but if their differences will create competitive advantage or not, depends on the situation. It could be the case that certain forms and directions of nepotism are well fitted to certain situations, while in other situations another kind of nepotism is more adequate, or even, not adequate at all. This indicates that nepotism could be managed in order to fit with the needs of the family and the firm.

Empirical exposition of nepotism in three cases of family business

The terminology of nepotism, as presented in Collin & Ahlberg (2022) and the derived implications of nepotism in this paper will here be used in order to analyse data from three case studies. We term the three corporations Red, Blue and Yellow. The data was collected through interviews, public information from annual reports and from newspapers.

In Red, we interviewed 5 person – four family members and one employee during 7,25 hours in total. In Blue we interviewed 7 persons – five from the family and two employees during 8,25 hours in total. In Yellow we interviewed 9 persons – five from the family and four employees during 14,5 hours in total. We used annual reports that gave us data for ten years, from 2003 to 2012. The interviews were conducted during summer and autumn 2013. During the interviews both researchers participated. Transcriptions of the interviews were made, and a summary of the interviews were sent to the interviewees in order to get their approval of the summary.

We listed the variables from the terminology of nepotism and from the nepotism implications and coded them in accordance with our definitions of the concepts and based on our experience and impressions from the cases. We gave a number between 0 to 1 for each variable, indicating 0 as absent category, to 1 indicating highly strong presence. Since this is subjective coding, we compared our coding and through discussion and returning to the interview data, we arrived at consensus on the single value on each variable. Thus, it is subjective, but the consensus debate creates a control on subjectivity and thus on interrater reliability.

Analysis

In this section we describe the outcome of our coding of the three cases and present the analysis of the correlations that can be found between our terminology of nepotism and implications of nepotism.

Below is table 2 showing the numbers of our coding, in sections describing the family concepts and the firm concepts showing the extension of nepotism in the family and the firm, where the mean is an expression of the extent of nepotism.

Red is a corporation producing consumer products that are sold to retailers. Its sales are about kSkr 43.000, i.e., about k€ 4.300 (€1H”SKr 10.1) and it has about 35 employees. It started 80 years ago, and today it is owned by two of the founding family’s five children, a brother and a sister. The board consists of the top management team, being the brother, the sister and the brother’s three children. The top management team does also include an employee that does not belong to the family. The generational nepotism is 1 since all available generations are engaged in

Table 2. Nepotism Analysis of three cases

	Red	Blue	Yellow
Family			
Generational nepotism	1,00	0,90	1,00
Kin nepotism	0,40	1,00	1,00
Nepotistic supply (mean)	0,70	0,95	1,00
Firm			
Nep hierarichal diffusion	0,90	0,70	0,90
Nep functional diffusion	0,90	0,80	0,90
Nepotistic impregnation	0,90	0,75	0,90
Mean	0,80	0,85	0,95
Pros and cons of nepotism			
Pros Firm Nepotism	0,99	0,59	0,61
Cons Firm Nepotism	0,20	0,28	0,20
Pros Family Nepotism	0,97	0,67	0,67
Cons Family Nepotism	0,00	0,10	0,00
Sum (Pros-Cons)	1,75	0,88	1,08

the firm, but the kin nepotism is only about 0.4 since only 2 out of five siblings in the oldest generation are engaged. However, it is only one of the five siblings that contribute with their family in the firm. Thus, a total supply on generation, but very restricted on kin, giving a nepotistic supply of 0.7. The firm is, however, highly impregnated by the family, both on the hierarchical dimension and the functional dimension, giving the nepotistic impregnation value of 0.9. The utilisation of the pros of nepotism were found to be very high and the cons of nepotism were mainly avoided, giving the sum of 1.75. Our understanding of this outcome is that the low level of kin nepotism reduces conflict in the family presence in the firm, with a very homogenous vision of the strategy and the goals of the corporation. This strong strategy, combined with strong presence of the family in the firm, gave high legitimacy to the family presence, i.e., to the strong nepotistic impregnation in the firm.

Blue is a corporation producing products within the transport industry. Its sales are about kSKr 120.000, i.e., about k€11900 and it has about 60 employees. It is about 40 years old. The founder and his wife are present at the board, but the management of the firm is performed by their daughter and son, with the daughter's husband as CEO, all of them members of the board. A child of the son is slightly engaged in the firm, but due to succession events ten years ago, there is strong hesitation of further succession. The generational nepotism is smaller than of the other two firms, but the kin nepotism, involving all but one sibling, gives a value of 1.0. Thus, the nepotistic supply is close to 1, only reduced due to the doubt of succession. The family being not so numerous makes the nepotistic impregnation less compared to Red. One position at the top management level is occupied by non-family members, thus giving a nepotistic hierarchical diffusion of 0.7. Functionally the family is more diffused, giving a slightly higher number. When inspecting the pros and cons of nepotism, all pros of nepotism are not utilized and due to the former succession events, some of the cons are slightly stronger than in the other firms. In sum, Blue receives still a total of positive implications of the nepotism, but lowest of the three firms. Our interpretation is that the former succession events created a hesitation in implementing nepotism.

Yellow is a corporation supplying products and services, mainly to households, but also to organizations. The sales is about kSKr 388.000, i.e., about k€38.400. The founder and wife are present at the board and their three sons are members of the board and have top management positions in the firm. The board consists of two more directors that are not of the family. Some children of the brothers, those that are of age, are engaged in the firm. Thus, the generational nepotism is 1.0 since all available generations participate. The kin nepotism is also 1.0, since all blood lines participate. Thus, Yellow has a very strong nepotistic supply. The diffusion in the firm is less, partly because of the size of the firm, but is still high. The effects of nepotism have been considered to be in between the other firms. They do not exploit all pros of nepotism, partly because predictability was interpreted as being low since a succession was not discernible. There is also an unbalanced influence on the firm by the three brothers, where one brother, the CEO, is acting strongly and entrepreneurial, while one

brother is unobtrusive, with a low profile in the corporation, probably showing a need of independence.

The analysis indicates that the utilization of nepotism was most intense in the red corporation with lower kin nepotism. Low levels of kin nepotism can assumably reduce the level of conflicts and give a fruitful soil for a strong vision and strategy. In Red, one of the siblings was engaged during some years, but decided to leave the firm. Our interpretation is that it was due to the leaving brother not sharing the vision of the other siblings in the firm. Thus, the strong nepotistic effects were due to the allocative mechanism, what could be termed nepotistic selection, where family members leave or stay depending on their benefits of the nepotism and if they share the vision of the dominant family members.

In the case of Blue, the exploitation of nepotism was lower, probably due to the former bad management of succession, where the children had to assume power, that they initially did not want. In this case, the sense of nepotism was lower, and its implications were less utilization of nepotism.

In the third case, the Yellow firm, the nepotistic implications are less, partly because of succession reasons, but also because the presence of the three brothers, that all are present, but in different ways. Where Red avoids tensions between many siblings, and gets a strong convincing vision and strategy, Yellow gets more of uncertainty and a vision that is not clear, and sometimes not even predictable. One conclusion is that exploitation of nepotism demands not only nepotistic impregnation but also a good management of nepotistic supply, where too diverse, i.e., high kin nepotism, run the risk of creating conflicts which reduce the benefits of nepotism.

Nepotism has been given negative values, as we indicated in the beginning. These values were not to be found in any of the three corporations. We believe that nepotistic impregnation is so strong in all three cases that nepotism is considered to be natural, i.e., legitimate. This could, however, be due to a selection bias, where people that would feel demotivated by nepotism do not accept employment in a family firm or leave the firm when they experience that their own development is hindered by nepotism. Thus, the pool of potential employees could be smaller for family firms, and the drop out of employees in career positions could be higher, thereby reducing the firm's opportunity to get the right person on

the right job. The conclusion is that the strength of nepotism considered being natural could be won with the price of restricted supply of labour.

Summary and conclusion

We have suggested that nepotism is the essence of family firms, and that it has its pros and cons. Listing pros and cons we could not theoretically show that nepotism is efficient, even if the goals are purely financial or socio-emotional wealth oriented. However, if the number of pros and cons tells any story, it is that there are at least no strong indications for the popular opinion of nepotism, that of it being negative, at least at this level of nepotism conception and theory development. Finally, by analysing three empirical cases, we found that utilization of nepotism was stronger if the family manages their nepotistic supply, especially concerning kin nepotism. We also found indications that less nepotism implies less nepotistic utility gained by the family and the family firm.

One implication of our results is that we could suggest that a family and a family firm can gain from a conscious governance strategy (Collin, 2007) including nepotistic selection and management of nepotism. Managing nepotism implies to emphasise it when there are possible advantages of it, and to avoid it when there are possible disadvantages of it, if possible, or to reduce it or to hide it, dependent on situation and wanted effects. For example, stressing the importance of keeping the organization to family values, nepotistic impregnation is a mean of infusing the organization with these values, which could establish a strong vision in the organization and create an organizational culture directing action and reducing deviations.

The management of nepotism has to consider the good and bad effects of nepotism in the family and the firm. In figure 1 we indicate what kind of management that could be preferred, due to the expected impact of nepotism.

Emphasize nepotism: If nepotism is good for both the family and the firm, it could be emphasized. This implies to stress both nepotistic supply and nepotistic impregnation. The situations driving this condition could be a highly dynamic firm environment where the firm needs certainty, which the nepotistic acts could create. This could be made through promoting family members stressing their family origin and them carrying the values

Corporation			
	<i>Good</i>	<i>Bad</i>	
Family	<i>Good</i>	Emphasize	Hide
	<i>Bad</i>	Reduce	Avoid

Figure 1. Management of nepotism

and experience of the family. Specific positions at the firm could be reserved for family members, and clearly expressed as family positions.

Hide nepotism: When nepotism is good for the family, but bad for the firm, it could be hidden. This implies that the nepotistic impregnation is suppressed. This could be done through legitimizing family recruitment through a) emphasising that the individuals have harder work to perform than non-family members since the family member has to be as competent as everyone else (cf. Ciulla, 2005) but in addition has to carry the tradition and to subordinate her/himself to the family and the destiny of the firm; b.) dog treatment, that a family member have to endure some employment time in positions on lower levels than motivated by their competence, or in positions that are considered to be strenuous (Muchinsky, 2012) and c) educating family members, preferably at prestigious schools, implying competence and ability.

Reduce nepotism: When nepotism is bad for the family, for example when it could create disincentives for effort, but is good for the corporation,

it could be reduced. This implies to reduce nepotistic supply and therefore to make highly strategic nepotistic impregnation. This could be done through promoting a family member that contradicts the nepotistic selection, for example, to promote a person married to a family member to a position previously held by a family member.

Avoid nepotism: When nepotism is bad for both the firm and the family, it could be avoided. This implies to reduce both nepotistic supply and nepotistic impregnation. This is however an event that is hard to imagine in a family firm since it would be to ‘de-list’ the firm as a family firm, thus losing the image and reputation of the firm as a family firm.

Concluding, we have indicated that nepotism is at the heart of a family business, and that it has such an impact on both the family and the business, that it is worth more attention, both in practice, as an intentional strategy and implemented through management of nepotism, and in research, as a concept worthy of being released from its negative and restrictive normative burdens. While the Parable of the Prodigal Son in the Gospel of Luke (15:11-32) is told by Christ in order to teach people about the virtue of forgiving, the researcher should avoid normative judgments. The researcher’s duty is to try to explain the father’s action and to find pros and cons of such an action.

References

1. Ahlberg, J (2021). *Boards of directors in family firms: Their functions and borders*, Linnaeus University Press: Vдхјц, 403/2021.
2. Barnett, T., & Kellermanns, F. W. (2006). Are We Family and Are We Treated as Family? Nonfamily Employees’ Perceptions of Justice in the Family Firm. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(6):837–854.
3. Bertrand, M., & Schoar, A. (2006). The Role of Family in Family Firms. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 20(2):73–96.
4. Bloom, N. & van Reenen (2007). Measuring and explaining management practices across firms and countries. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 122(4):1351-1408.
5. Ciulla, J. B. (2005). Review article: In praise of nepotism? *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 15(1):153–160.
6. Collin, S.-O., (2007). Governance strategy: a property right approach turning governance into action. *Journal of Management & Governance*, 11:215-237.

7. Collin, S.-O. & Ahlberg, J. (2022). Nepotism in family firms – a terminology. Вчені зап. Харків. гуманітар. ун-ту «Нар. укр. акад.», т. 28, (Scientific collection of KhHU «People's Ukrainian Academy», vol. 28:171-185).

8. Collin, S.-O. & Smith, E. (2007). Window of entrepreneurship – Explaining the influence of corporate governance mechanisms on corporate entrepreneurship in two riding schools, *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship & Small Business*, 4(2):122-137.

9. Chua, J. H., Chrisman, J. J., & Sharma, P. (1999). Defining the family business by behavior. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 23:19–40.

10. Dickson, M. W., Nieminen, L. R. G. and Biermeier-Hanson, B. J. (2012). Nepotism and organizational homogeneity: How the ASA process is accelerated by nonmerit-based decision making, In: Jones, R. G. ed. 2012. *Nepotism in Organizations*, NY: Routledge, Ch. 5.

11. Distelberg, B. J., & Blow, A. (2011). Variations in Family System Boundaries. *Family Business Review*, 24(1): 28–46.

12. Doeringer, P. B., & Piore, M. J. (1971). *Internal Labor Markets and Manpower Analysis*. Lexington, Mass.: Heath.

13. Gevrek, D. & Gevrek, Z. E. (2010) Nepotism, incentives and the academic success of college students, *Labour Economics*, 17):581-591.

14. van Hooft, E. A. J. and Stout, T. (2012). Nepotism and career choice, job search, and job choice, In: Jones, R. G. ed. 2012. *Nepotism in Organizations*, NY: Routledge, Ch. 4.

15. Jaskiewicz, P., Uhlenbruck, K., Balkin, D. B. & Reay, T. (2013). Is nepotism good or bad? Types of nepotism and implications for knowledge management. *Family Business Review*, 26(2):121-139.

16. Karra, N., Tracey, P., & Phillips, N. (2006). Altruism and Agency in the Family Firm: Exploring the Role of Family, Kinship, and Ethnicity. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(6): 861–877.

17. Kragh, S. U. (2012) The anthropology of nepotism: Social distance and reciprocity in organizations in developing countries. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, 12(2):247-265.

18. Lane, S., Astrachan, J. H., Keyt, A., & McMillan, K. (2006). Guidelines for Family Business Boards of Directors. *Family Business Review*, 19(2):147–167.

19. Le Breton-Miller, I., & Miller, D. (2008). To grow or to harvest? Governance, strategy and performance in family and lone founder firms. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 1(1):41–56.

20. Lubatkin, M. H., Schulze, W. S., Ling, Y., & Dino, R. N. (2005). The effects of parental altruism on the governance of family-managed firms. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(3):313–330.

21. Mhatre, K. H., Riggio, R. E. and Riggio, H. R. (2012) Nepotism and leadership, In: Jones, R. G. ed. 2012. *Nepotism in Organizations*, NY: Routledge, Ch. 8
22. Muchinsky, P. M. (2012). The nepotistic organization: What is this place and how do the people make it? In: Jones, R. G. ed. 2012. *Nepotism in Organizations*, NY: Routledge, Ch. 3
23. Neyer, F. J., & Lang, F. R. (2003). Blood is thicker than water: Kinship orientation across adulthood. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 84(2):310–321.
24. Salvato, C., Minichilli, A. & Piccarreta, R. (2012) Faster route to the CEO suite: Nepotism or managerial proficiency? *Family Business Review*, 25(2):206–224.
25. Schulze, W. S., Lubatkin, M. H., Dino, R. N., & Buchholtz, A. K. (2001). Agency Relationships in Family Firms: Theory and Evidence. *Organization Science*, 12(2):99–116.
26. Spranger, J. L., Colarelli, S. M., Dimotakis, N., Jacob, A. C. & Arvey, R. D. (2012) Effects of kin density within family-owned businesses, *Organizational behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 119:151-162.
27. Vallejo, M. C. (2008) Is the culture of the family firms really different? A value-based model for its survival through generations, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 81:261-279.
28. Vinton, K. L. (1998). Nepotism: An Interdisciplinary Model. *Family Business Review*, 11(4):297–303.
29. Webb, J. W., Ketchen, D. J., & Ireland, R. D. (2010). Strategic entrepreneurship within family-controlled firms: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 1(2):67–77.